

DOI :

Nurse workload and patient safety in hospital settings: A cross-sectional study

Philatheitha Mungleng* Kriti Sharma** Sumant Swain***

*Nursing Manager, Aakash Healthcare Super Specialty Hospital Pvt. Ltd., Dwarka, New Delhi, India.

**PGDM, International Institute of Health Management Research, New Delhi, India.

***Assistant Professor, International Institute of Health Management Research, New Delhi, India.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Patient safety is a critical component of high-quality nursing care and healthcare delivery systems. The heavy workload of hospital nurses is one of the key difficulties linked with the health care system, and there are substantial implications associated with too much pressure on nursing staff. The objective of the paper is to analyze the workflows of hospital staff nurses and to identify the root cause of the causal relationship between heavy nurse workload and patient safety. **Material and Methods:** This cross-sectional study design using a mixed technique approach was conducted in Aakash Healthcare Super Specialty Hospital Pvt, Ltd., New Delhi, India. This study included 120 inpatient department (IPD) patients, 10 clinical and 40 nursing staff in May 2022. To conduct data collection surveys, a semi-structured questionnaire was developed. **Results:** The rising workload of staff nurses causes a communication chasm between nurses and physicians, significantly impacting the quality of nurse-physician collaboration. Factors related to staff nurses' excessive workload influence the prevalence of medication mistakes and nosocomial infections. According to this study, heavy workload is a major source of occupational stress for nurses and has a negative influence on patient safety. **Conclusion:** The key factors of nursing workload include staffing numbers, patient conditions, and the architecture of nurses; work systems. The workload on nurses should be properly measured, and work system elements that contribute to the workload should be identified. Increasing nursing personnel and maintaining an appropriate nurse-patient ratio are critical steps toward improving patient safety. Quality nursing care and efficient management of workload among nurses can provide a better life to patients and human beings.

Keywords: Patient safety, nurse workload, nursing quality, health system, mixed method, medication error, nosocomial infection, and nurse-patient ratio.

INTRODUCTION

The enormous workload of nurses at hospitals is a major problem throughout the healthcare sector. Nursing workers are under more work pressure than ever before, especially since COVID-19 (1). Growing healthcare consumer demand, an insufficient nursing staff, and the accompanying increasing working overtime are all variables contributing to nurses' increased workload. The significant critical care burden of Nursing personnel

ACCESS THIS ARTICLE ONLINE	
Quick Response Code:	Available online at : thirdvoice.voiceforvoiceless.in
	DOI: Article No - TVRV00066

Address for correspondence :			
Dr. Sumant Swain, Assistant Professor, International Institute of Health Management Research, Sector 18 A, Plot no 3, Dwarka, New Delhi, Pin:110067, India. Email: sumanta.swain@gmail.com, ORCID ID: https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2513-1739			
© The Author(s) 2024. Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/ .			
For reprints contact: voiceforvoiceless2013@gmail.com			
Received	Reviewed	Accepted	Published
02-Feb.-2024	27-Mar.-2024	22-Apr.-2024	10-Jun.-2024
Volume	Issue	Nov.	ISSN
No. 6	No. 1	2024	2583-1852(P), 2584-0878(O)
How to Cite this Article: Philatheitha; Sharma, Kriti; and Swain, Sumant. Nurse workload and patient safety in hospital settings: A cross-sectional study. THE THIRD VOICE REALITY AND VISION. 2024. Vol No-6. Issue No-1. June. Pp: 119-125 DOI			

tends to be associated with inadequate care provided by nurses, dissatisfaction among patients, and the amount of time that nursing workers commit to their different duties (2) . Nurse workload and patient outcomes, as well as nurse-reported quality of care, are interconnected (3) (4) (5) (6). Workload is an indication of exhaustion and absenteeism; therefore, appropriate management of workload will also help workers stay healthy (7) . Bakker discovered a link between employment demands like workload and performance (8) . Toh et al (9) observed a positive bidirectional association between the nursing shortage and work dissatisfaction, stress, and burnout among oncology registered nurses (10) . Nurses, on the other hand, play a crucial role in ensuring patient safety in addition to delivering individualised care. Even the most seriously sick hospitalised patient may only spend 30 to 45 minutes a day with a physician as they make diagnostic and therapeutic choices, limiting their capacity to detect changes in a patient's health over time (11) . Nurses are always at the patients bedside, frequently conversing with physicians, chemists, families, and the rest of the health care team, and they are essential to the team's efficient coordination and transmission of the patient's status. A nurse's role in patient safety includes monitoring patients for clinical improvement, detecting errors and near misses, understanding care procedures and system flaws, identifying and communicating changes in patient condition, and performing a plethora of other tasks to ensure patients receive high-quality care (12).

The ability of nurses to provide bedside care is important to their capability to keep patients safe. As a result, allocating an increasing number of patients jeopardises a nurses ability to provide safe care. The severity of patients, registration numbers, payment transfers, hospital discharges, staff skill mix and experience, the physical design of the nursing unit, and the availability of technology and other resources are all important factors to consider while staffing a nursing unit (13) .

Nurses' higher levels of effort and stress, as well as the risk of burnout, are primarily likely addressing the causal link between nurse-to-patient ratios and patient outcomes. Nursing's high-intensity nature puts workers at risk of making errors when performing basic medical services. When a person performs a challenging function, such as providing medications to a hospitalised patient, the work environment should be as conducive to that task as possible, according to human factors engineering principles. However, operational issues such as interruptions or equipment failures may make it

impossible for nurses to do such responsibilities in a safe and effective manner. According to several research, nurses' work are frequently interrupted (15) . While certain disruptions in patient care are inevitable, the relationship between interruptions and mistakes is another instance of how defects in nurses' daily work environments are significantly tied to patient safety (16) . The primary objective of this paper is to look at the work patterns of hospital staff nurses in order to find the underlying relationship between excessive nurse workload and patient safety.

Material and Methods

The study used a Mixed-Method approach, wherein both qualitative and quantitative approaches were used and followed a cross-sectional design. It addressed the development, validation, and evaluation of research tools. Semi-structured questionnaire and daily feedback

were collected from patients admitted to hospitals (IPD) and all nursing staff, regarding nursing workload and patient care satisfaction in May 2022. This study was conducted in Aakash health care super specialty hospital, Dwarka, New Delhi, India. This is a 200 bedded multi-specialty hospital. The value of Aakash Hospital is ICARE. Which means Integrity, Compassion, Accountability, Respect and Excellence. It has all specialties including emergency, critical care, general medicine, geriatric medicine, oncology, cardiology, neurology, nephrology, gastroenterology, pulmonology, an orthopaedic ward, and a separate high-tech dialysis department and radiology department are also available. In this study, the population includes all IPD patients and nursing staff in Aakash Hospital. Study samples were collected from nursing staff (4 th floor), for both surgical and medical patients who were admitted to Aakash Hospital, Dwarka through random sampling. The sample size included 120 IPD patients, 10 clinical and 40 nursing staff. The study was analysed in Excel, and the percentages were shown in graphs and tables. This study was obtained ethical approval from IIHMR student research board. The respondents were given details about the study's confidentiality, voluntary participation, benefits, the freedom to leave at any moment and importance of the responses. The written consent form was signed before the start of the study.

Results

Medication error frequently happened in many hospitals. Data captured were analysed and it shown medication error compliance for 3 months. Figure 1: data reflects

that there was a high number of missed doses in the month of October followed by December and November in the total number of errors. The total percentage of error in month of October, November and December were 45 percent, 30 percent and 40 percent respectively.

This study reveals that in the normal ward, the nurse and patient ratio is 1:5 and the nurse has to visit every patient 3 times just for medication in a shift excluding attending call bells, Doctor’s rounds, Dressing, and some minor procedures (Table:1). So, for medication if 3X1:5=1:15 times visits for total patients. And if the ratio is changed to 1:6 then the total visits for medication per one nurse is equal to 18 times visits/shift. Again taking 1:7=21visits/shift.

Table 1: Nurse workload and patient ratio

Nurse	Number of Patients	Visiting per Patient only for Medication	Others Responsibilities
1 Staff	5 Patients	3 Times/ Patients = 15 Times	Call Bell Response,
1 Staff	6 Patients	3 Times/ Patients = 18 Times	Doctors Rounds, Dressing,
1Staff	7 Patients	3 Times/ Patients = 21 Times	Documentation on Systemic.

Therefore, if the nurse workload increases, it is logical that the nurse needs to work more rapidly to complete the tasks within his/her shift due to which the medication for patient “A” is given to patient “B” or inaccurate medication (Timeliness) due to attending other extra responsibilities like attending Call bell, dressing, etc. which increase in error of medication by the nurse and missed dose of medication.

To avoid errors in medication, do the MAR sheet auditing daily by the Clinical Pharmacist and medication reconciliation is done by every shift nurse. Medication reconciliation is a critical healthcare practise that entails establishing an accurate prescription list for patients. Audits on a regular basis can help to eliminate mistakes and enhance patient safety. Policy, patient documentation, communication, electronic health record use, and collaboration with chemists are all important markers. Regular evaluations and changes can help to improve these procedures. As shown in Table.1 the Patient ratio is reduced to 1:5/less as per the criticality of the patient.

After introducing MAR sheet auditing, post-analysis on the error of medication is done which is shown in Table 2 for the months of January, February, March, and April.

Table 2: Post analysis on the error of medication from January to April 2022

Errors	Wrong route	Wrong dose	missed dose	Wrong indent	Wrong administration	Error-prone abbreviation	Total errors	Percentage
January	7	5	6	7	4	3	32	32%
February	5	2	4	6	3	4	24	24%
March	2	3	3	4	1	2	15	15%
April	0	2	2	1	1	2	8	8%

The total monthly Analysis of seven months for medication error is shown in figure 2 including both after and before introducing MAR sheet auditing which shows the maximum in the month of October and the least during April.

There is a graphics illustrating the fundamental cause of lowering nursing workload and assuring patient safety after compliance with nurses’ workload and patient safety.

Figure 3: Diagram to reduce nursing workload and ensure patient safety

According to the observations and survey results, patient safety is about using evidence-based practises to generate positive health outcomes and avoiding dangerous behaviours to prevent medication mistakes. Patient safety is an important aspect of nurses’ duties; when patient care is dangerous, nurses endure moral distress.

Figure 4: Errors in patient safety due to nursing workload

issues contribute to a higher patient ratio, increased work overload, and a lack of effective communication between nurses and physicians.

Furthermore, nurses with balanced workloads had greater levels of job satisfaction, mental/physical well-being, and continuing employment. This lowers the expenses of nursing burnout, absenteeism, recruiting, and retention. Finally, effective nursing workload management leads in safer patients, increased nurses' satisfaction with their (work) life, and cost savings (Table 3).

Table 3: Relationship between nurses' workload and patient safety.

Mechanisms	Description	Examples
Time	Nurses that have an intense workload may not have the time to do their duties effectively, use safe practises, or assess patients, and as a result, their communication with physicians and other providers may suffer.	There is no time or very little time to double-check medicines.
Motivation	Nurses with an intense caseload may be unsatisfied with their professions, lowering their incentive to perform well.	There is little or minimal drive or dedication to increasing efficiency. Workload saturation causes dissatisfaction and the emergence of a bad attitude towards what one accomplishes.
Stress and burnout	Long-shift nurses may endure stress and burnout, which may reduce their efficacy.	Nurses' physical and cognitive resources are limited, making it difficult for them to work properly.
Errors in decision-making (Attention)	A heavy intellectual load (part of the nursing task) might contribute to slippage, missteps, or errors.	Failure to give drugs
Violations or Workaround	A heavy workload may make it more difficult for nurses to follow rules and regulations, jeopardising the quality and safety of patient care.	Hand washing is enough.
Systemic or organizational impact	A physician's, nurse management's, or another provider's severe workload may jeopardise the integrity of therapy provided by an extra nurse.	When other nurses require assistance with their patients, a charge nurse may not be available.

DISCUSSION

Among the various difficulties addressed are the task's high risk, higher stress levels triggered by workload and distractions, and the possibility of burnout due to involvement in error. Thus, the changing healthcare environment has mostly led to nurses' high workload. The need for nurses in the health care system has risen

as the population has aged. Furthermore, an insufficient supply of nurses and lowered staffing levels have forced nurses to work overtime. The above-mentioned trend in health care practise has had an impact on nurse workload, quality of treatment, and patient safety. Workplace variables and staffing levels can influence nurses' work satisfaction and dedication to providing high-quality care (17). Workloads can cause qualitative

and quantitative discontent among nurses. Close patient supervision, excessive effort for patient health and safety, and ongoing direct interaction with clients are examples of quantitative overload. Inadequate knowledge and abilities, family demands for patient safety, significant accountability in nursing care, and hospital leadership expectations all contribute to qualitative overload (18). High workload can also increase communication gaps between nurses and physicians, leading to job dissatisfaction and increased job dissatisfaction among nurses performance barriers exert a negative influence on their workload and standard of life at work. Aside from equipment-related issues, performance obstacles impacted reported safety and effectiveness of care, with workload acting as a moderator. In general, performance barriers increase nursing workload, lowering the perceived quality and safety of treatment (19).

However, many nurses have complained that they have lost enthusiasm at work as a result of the increased workload, which has contributed to a significant number of mistakes and patient safety 11 concerns. The mental stress of nurses has grown due to the complicated work environment and the requirement to work beyond hours. Because a high nursing workload can have an influence on nurse productivity, satisfaction, turnover rate, job stress, and patient safety, solutions to lower the workload strain of nurses in care are required. Patient adverse events were highly impacted by non-nursing task experience. Nurses performing non-nursing jobs were more likely to encounter falls, nosocomial infections, pressure sores, and prescription mistakes (20). The bed-to-nurse ratio increased the occurrence of pressure ulcers. Nurses who thought the nursing staff was enough were less likely to have pressure sores. Medication errors were lower in hospitals where a large proportion of nurses believed the staff was adequate.

CONCLUSION

With the occurrence of missing medicine, communication gaps between nurses and physicians, absenteeism, and turnover, the number of patients allocated to nursing staff each day rose significantly. According to the findings of this study, the bigger the number of patients assigned to nurses each day, and the lower the rate of patient satisfaction with the nursing team. Nursing personnel with fewer patients assigned had the greatest results for patient safety indicators linked to care and management. As a result, the Nurse-patient ratio must be set for patient safety depending on

the patient's needs and criticality. Patient safety entails using evidence-based practises to produce positive health outcomes and avoiding risky behaviours to decrease medication mistakes. Patient safety is a critical component of nurses' jobs; when patient care is dangerous, nurses endure moral discomfort. Furthermore, nurses with balanced workloads had greater levels of job satisfaction, mental/physical well-being, and continuing employment. This decreases nurse burnout, absenteeism, and other issues. The nurse-patient ratio should be determined by the patient's state and criticality. Recreation hours such as Yoga, Zumba, Meditation, and so on should be offered to nurses in order to relieve stress, demotivation, weariness, and anxiety. Training should be provided for nurses on topics of interest, such as language classes, public speaking confidence, effective communication, and so on.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

PM and SS conceptualized and designed the study, collected data, analyzed and interpreted the data, and drafted the manuscript. KS contributed to the discussion part and reviewed it critically. All the authors provided critical input on the paper, read and approved the final paper. SS takes responsibility as a guarantor for this research article.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the International Institute of Health Management (IIHMR) student research board.

Informed Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank all the participants who patiently participated in this study. Thanks to the IIHMR, Delhi, and Aakash Healthcare Care Super Specialty Hospital, Dwarka, New Delhi for providing support and cooperation to complete this study.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT AND SPONSORSHIP

Nil.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES :

1. Souza D. Health of nursing professionals: workload during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Rev Bras Med Trab.* 2020 Jan 1;18:464–71.
2. Zahednezhad H, shokrollahi N, Gheshlagh RG, Afshar PF. Does heavy mental workload affect moral sensitivity among critical care unit nursing professionals? a cross-sectional study. *BMC Nurs [Internet].* 2021 Aug 10 [cited 2023 Nov 13];20(1):140. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-021-00662-8>
3. Aiken LH, Sloane DM, Bruyneel L, Van den Heede K, Griffiths P, Busse R, et al. Nurse staffing and education and hospital mortality in nine European countries: a retrospective observational study. *Lancet Lond Engl.* 2014 May 24;383(9931):1824–30.
4. Exploring the Association Between Nurse Workload and Nurse-Sensitive Patient Safety Outcome Indicators: Retraction. *J Nurs Res JNR.* 2022 Jun 1;30(3):e215.
5. Unruh L. Nurse staffing and patient, nurse, and financial outcomes. *Am J Nurs.* 2008 Jan;108(1):62–71; quiz 72.
6. Hinno S, Partanen P, Vehviläinen-Julkunen K. Nursing activities, nurse staffing and adverse patient outcomes as perceived by hospital nurses. *J Clin Nurs.* 2012 Jun;21(11–12):1584–93.
7. Van Bogaert P, Clarke S, Willems R, Mondelaers M. Staff engagement as a target for managing work environments in psychiatric hospitals: implications for workforce stability and quality of care. *J Clin Nurs.* 2013 Jun;22(11–12):1717–28.
8. Spence Laschinger HK, Grau AL, Finegan J, Wilk P. Predictors of new graduate nurses' workplace well-being: testing the job demands-resources model. *Health Care Manage Rev.* 2012;37(2):175–86.
9. Toh SG, Ang E, Devi MK. Systematic review on the relationship between the nursing shortage and job satisfaction, stress and burnout levels among nurses in oncology/haematology settings. *Int J Evid Based Healthc.* 2012 Jun;10(2):126–41. 13
10. Oetelaar WFJM van den, Stel HF van, Rhenen W van, Stellato RK, Grolman W. Balancing nurses' workload in hospital wards: study protocol of developing a method to manage workload. *BMJ Open [Internet].* 2016 Nov 1 [cited 2023 Nov 13];6(11):e012148. Available from: <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/6/11/e012148>
11. Nursing and Patient Safety | PSNet [Internet]. [cited 2023 Nov 13]. Available from: <https://psnet.ahrq.gov/primer/nursing-and-patient-safety>
12. Vaismoradi M, Tella S, A. Logan P, Khakurel J, Vizcaya-Moreno F. Nurses' Adherence to Patient Safety Principles: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health [Internet].* 2020 Mar [cited 2023 Nov 13];17(6):2028. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7142993/>
13. Butler M, Schultz TJ, Halligan P, Sheridan A, Kinsman L, Rotter T, et al. Hospital nurse staffing models and patient and staff related outcomes. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev [Internet].* 2019 Apr 23 [cited 2023 Nov 13];2019(4):CD007019. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6478038/>
14. Ohue T, Moriyama M, Nakaya T. Examination of a cognitive model of stress, burnout, and intention to resign for Japanese nurses. *Jpn J Nurs Sci JJNS.* 2011 Jun;8(1):76–86.
15. Tucker AL, Spear SJ. Operational Failures and Interruptions in Hospital Nursing. *Health Serv Res [Internet].* 2006 Jun [cited 2023 Nov 13];41(3 Pt 1):643–62. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1713207/>
16. Monteiro C, Avelar AFM, Pedreira M da LG. Interruptions of nurses' activities and patient safety: an integrative literature review. *Rev Lat Am Enfermagem [Internet].* 2015 [cited 2023 Nov 13];23(1):169–79. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4376046/>
17. Carayon P, Gurses AP. Nursing Workload and Patient Safety—A Human Factors Engineering Perspective. In: Hughes RG, editor. *Patient Safety and Quality: An Evidence-Based Handbook for Nurses [Internet].* Rockville (MD): Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (US); 2008 [cited 2023 Nov 13]. (Advances in Patient Safety). Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK2657/>
18. Saputera B, Suhermin S. UNDERSTANDING NURSE WORKLOAD, WORK STRESS, AND SUPERVISION ON INFLUENCE OF CLINICAL PERFORMANCE. *Int Conf Bus Soc Sci [Internet].* 2020 Oct 4 [cited 2023 Nov 13]; Available from: <https://ojsicobuss.stiesia.ac.id/index.php/icobuss1st/article/view/18>
19. Impact of Performance Obstacles on Intensive Care Nurses' Workload, Perceived Quality and Safety of Care, and Quality of Working Life - PMC [Internet]. [cited 2023 Nov 13]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2677047/>
20. Kang JH, Kim CW, Lee SY. Nurse-Perceived Patient Adverse Events depend on the Nursing Workload. *Osong Public Health Res Perspect.* 2016 Feb;7(1):56–62.